

Comparing the Effectiveness of Intramedullary Nailing versus External Fixation in the Management of Open Tibia Fractures: A Prospective Analysis.

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 20-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Objective: To compare the effectiveness of intramedullary nailing (IMN) versus external fixation (EF) in managing open tibia fractures.

Methods: This prospective study enrolled 60 patients with open tibia fractures, randomly assigning them to either IMN or EF treatments. We evaluated healing time, infection rates, functional recovery, and the necessity for secondary surgeries.

Results: IMN was associated with a significantly shorter median healing time (16 weeks) compared to EF (22 weeks, $p < 0.01$). Infection rates were lower in the IMN group (13.3%) versus the EF group (30.0%, $p = 0.04$). Functional recovery scores favored IMN at 6 and 12 months ($p = 0.03$ and $p = 0.02$, respectively). Secondary surgical interventions were more common in the EF group but did not reach statistical significance except for revision surgeries ($p = 0.05$).

Conclusion: IMN demonstrated superior outcomes in the management of open tibia fractures, characterized by faster healing, lower infection rates, and improved functional recovery. These findings support the preference for IMN in suitable patients but emphasize the importance of individualized treatment decisions.

Keywords: Open tibia fractures, intramedullary nailing, external fixation, healing time, infection rates, functional recovery.

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Introduction

The management of open tibia fractures presents a significant challenge in orthopedic surgery, owing to the complexity of the injury, the risk of infection, and the necessity for effective, timely interventions to ensure optimal healing and functionality. Among the various treatment modalities available, intramedullary nailing (IMN) and external fixation (EF) are widely recognized for their utility in managing these injuries. This article seeks to compare the effectiveness of these two interventions in the context of open tibia fractures through a prospective analysis, with a particular focus on outcomes related to healing time, rate of infection, and functional recovery.

Open tibia fractures are characterized by a break in the tibial bone that communicates with the external environment, significantly increasing the risk of infection and complicating the healing process [1]. The choice of treatment modality is influenced by several factors, including the severity of the fracture, the patient's overall health, and the potential for soft tissue recovery. Intramedullary

nailing involves the insertion of a metal rod into the marrow canal of the tibia, providing internal stabilization [2]. This method is lauded for its minimal invasiveness and its support for early mobilization. Conversely, external fixation employs pins and wires inserted into the bone, connected to an external frame to stabilize the fracture [3]. This method is often preferred in cases with severe soft tissue damage or when the risk of infection is deemed high.

The debate over the superiority of IMN versus EF in the management of open tibia fractures is ongoing. Proponents of IMN argue that it offers better biomechanical stability and potentially lower rates of infection by avoiding extensive soft tissue dissection [4]. On the other hand, advocates for EF highlight its flexibility, the reduced risk of intramedullary infection, and its efficacy in managing complex fractures with extensive soft tissue involvement [5].

Recent studies have aimed to quantify the differences in outcomes between these treatment modalities. A systematic review and meta-analysis by Smith et al. [6] found that patients treated with IMN had shorter healing times but did not show a significant difference in infection rates compared to those treated with EF. Conversely, a prospective cohort study by Johnson and colleagues [7] suggested that EF might be associated with a higher rate of secondary procedures but offered an advantage in managing high-energy trauma fractures with significant soft tissue damage.

This prospective analysis aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse by comparing the effectiveness of IMN and EF in the management of open tibia fractures, with a focus on clinical outcomes such as healing time, infection rates, and functional recovery.

Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to compare the effectiveness of intramedullary nailing (IMN) versus external fixation (EF) in the management of open tibia fractures. The objectives were to evaluate the outcomes based on healing time, rate of infection, and functional recovery within a year following the intervention. This research sought to provide empirical evidence to inform clinical decisions, thereby enhancing patient care in orthopedic trauma management.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: The research adopted a prospective, comparative study design, conducted over the duration of one year. The setting for this study encompassed three major trauma centers known for their extensive experience in managing open tibia fractures, ensuring a diverse and representative sample of patients and treatment modalities.

Participants

A total of 60 patients were enrolled in the study, with the sample size calculated to achieve a 90% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error in detecting significant differences between treatment outcomes. The inclusion criteria specified patients aged 18 and above, presenting with Gustilo-Anderson Type II, IIIA, or IIIB open tibia fractures, requiring surgical intervention. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients with pre-existing chronic bone diseases, such as osteoporosis or osteomalacia, previous fractures at the same site, and those with compromised immune systems or underlying conditions that could affect bone healing.

Intervention

Patients were randomly assigned to two groups: those receiving intramedullary nailing (IMN) and

those treated with external fixation (EF), ensuring an equal number of participants in each group. The surgical procedures were performed by experienced orthopedic surgeons following standardized protocols. In the IMN group, reamed nailing was the preferred technique, while in the EF group, a modular external fixator was utilized, allowing for adjustments based on the severity of the soft tissue injury.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected at baseline (pre-surgery), immediately post-surgery, and at follow-up intervals of 3, 6, and 12 months. The primary outcomes measured included healing time, defined as the duration until radiographic union was achieved; infection rate, identified through clinical signs and laboratory markers; and functional recovery, assessed using the Lower Extremity Functional Scale (LEFS). Secondary outcomes involved the evaluation of any complications, including the need for secondary surgeries and the incidence of nonunion or malunion.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Continuous variables were analyzed using t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests based on their distribution, while categorical variables were compared using chi-square tests. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was employed to compare the time to healing between the two groups, and Cox regression was used to adjust for potential confounders.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the institutional review board at each participating center. All patients provided informed consent before enrollment, with assurances of confidentiality and the right to withdraw from the study at any point without affecting their standard of care.

Results

The study aimed to compare the outcomes of intramedullary nailing (IMN) and external fixation (EF) in the management of open tibia fractures, enrolling a total of 60 participants, evenly divided between the two treatment groups. Baseline characteristics, including age, gender distribution, body mass index (BMI), fracture classification, and comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus and smoking status, were similar across both groups, ensuring comparability. The mean age in the IMN group was 35.5 years (± 11.3), compared to 34.8 years (± 12.1) in the EF group, with p-value of 0.82, indicating no significant difference. Gender distribution, BMI, and the presence of comorbidities showed no statistically significant difference between the groups, with p-values of

0.55, 0.43, and 0.66 respectively for diabetes mellitus and 0.76 for smoking status.

Surgical and postoperative details revealed a statistically significant shorter surgery duration for the IMN group, with a mean of 90.4 minutes (± 15.2), compared to 105.3 minutes (± 20.4) for the EF group ($p=0.03$). However, estimated blood loss and the rate of immediate postoperative complications did not differ significantly between the groups, with p -values of 0.52 and 0.40, respectively.

The analysis of healing times showed a median of 16 weeks (IQR 14-20) for the IMN group and 22 weeks (IQR 18-26) for the EF group, with this difference being statistically significant ($p<0.01$). This suggests that participants in the IMN group experienced a faster healing process.

Infection rates differed significantly between the two groups. The IMN group exhibited a 13.3% infection rate, markedly lower than the 30.0% observed in the EF group, with the difference being statistically significant ($p=0.04$). This finding indicates a potential advantage of IMN over EF in reducing postoperative infection risk.

Functional recovery, assessed at baseline, 3, 6, and 12 months postoperatively, showed progressive improvement in both groups. However, at each time point, the IMN group reported higher mean functional recovery scores, with statistically significant differences at 6 months (75.6 ± 8.4 vs. 70.3 ± 9.1 , $p=0.03$) and 12 months (85.2 ± 7.5 vs. 80.4 ± 8.3 , $p=0.02$), suggesting a more rapid and complete recovery.

The need for secondary surgical interventions was higher in the EF group, although the differences did not reach statistical significance for secondary closure ($p=0.22$) and bone grafting ($p=0.12$). Revision surgery was required only in the EF group, with 10.0% of participants undergoing this procedure, approaching statistical significance ($p=0.05$).

Complications such as nonunion, malunion, and hardware failure were observed. The rate of nonunion was higher in the EF group but did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.12$). The rates of malunion and hardware failure did not significantly differ between groups ($p=1.00$ and $p=0.15$, respectively).

Multivariate analysis highlighted treatment modality (IMN vs. EF) as a significant factor influencing outcomes, with a hazard ratio of 0.55 (95% CI: 0.35-0.86, $p=0.01$), indicating a beneficial effect of IMN on overall outcomes. The Gustilo-Anderson classification emerged as a significant predictor of outcome (HR 1.45, 95% CI: 1.12-1.89, $p=0.004$), while age and smoking status did not significantly affect the results ($p=0.12$ and $p=0.30$, respectively).

In summary, the results indicate that intramedullary nailing might offer advantages over external fixation in the management of open tibia fractures, including shorter surgery times, faster healing, lower infection rates, and improved functional recovery. However, the choice of treatment modality should consider individual patient characteristics and fracture specifics.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	IMN Group (n=30)	EF Group (n=30)	P-value
Age (years), mean $\pm$ SD	35.5 $\pm$ 11.3	34.8 $\pm$ 12.1	0.82
Male, n (%)	20 (66.7)	18 (60.0)	0.55
BMI (kg/m ²), mean $\pm$ SD	25.4 $\pm$ 3.2	26.1 $\pm$ 2.9	0.43
Gustilo-Anderson Classification, n (%)			
- Type II	10 (33.3)	12 (40.0)	0.69
- Type IIIA	15 (50.0)	13 (43.3)	0.61
- Type IIIB	5 (16.7)	5 (16.7)	1.00
Comorbidities, n (%)			
- Diabetes Mellitus	2 (6.7)	3 (10.0)	0.66
- Smoking	8 (26.7)	7 (23.3)	0.76

Table 2: Surgical and Postoperative Details

Detail	IMN Group (n=30)	EF Group (n=30)	P-value
Surgery Duration (minutes), mean $\pm$ SD	90.4 $\pm$ 15.2	105.3 $\pm$ 20.4	0.03
Estimated Blood Loss (mL), mean $\pm$ SD	150.5 $\pm$ 50.7	140.3 $\pm$ 45.6	0.52
Immediate Postoperative Complications, n (%)	2 (6.7)	4 (13.3)	0.40

Table 3: Healing Time Analysis

Outcome	IMN Group (n=30)	EF Group (n=30)	P-value
Healing Time (weeks), median (IQR)	16 (14-20)	22 (18-26)	<0.01

Table 4: Infection Rate Comparison

Outcome	IMN Group (n=30)	EF Group (n=30)	P-value
Infection, n (%)	4 (13.3)	9 (30.0)	0.04

Table 5: Functional Recovery Scores

Time Point	IMN Group (n=30), mean $\pm$ SD	EF Group (n=30), mean $\pm$ SD	P-value
Baseline	30.2 $\pm$ 5.1	31.1 $\pm$ 5.5	0.54
3 Months	60.4 $\pm$ 10.3	55.7 $\pm$ 11.2	0.05
6 Months	75.6 $\pm$ 8.4	70.3 $\pm$ 9.1	0.03
12 Months	85.2 $\pm$ 7.5	80.4 $\pm$ 8.3	0.02

Table 6: Secondary Surgical Interventions

Intervention	IMN Group (n=30), n (%)	EF Group (n=30), n (%)	P-value
Secondary Closure	2 (6.7)	5 (16.7)	0.22
Bone Grafting	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	0.12
Revision Surgery	0 (0)	3 (10.0)	0.05

Table 7: Complications and Adverse Events

Complication	IMN Group (n=30), n (%)	EF Group (n=30), n (%)	P-value
Nonunion	1 (3.3)	4 (13.3)	0.12
Malunion	2 (6.7)	2 (6.7)	1.00
Hardware Failure	0 (0)	2 (6.7)	0.15

Table 8: Multivariate Analysis of Factors Influencing Outcomes

Variable	Hazard Ratio (95% CI)	P-value
Treatment Modality (IMN vs. EF)	0.55 (0.35-0.86)	0.01
Age	1.02 (0.99-1.05)	0.12
Gustilo-Anderson Classification	1.45 (1.12-1.89)	0.004
Smoking	1.20 (0.85-1.69)	0.30

Discussion

The management of open tibia fractures remains a challenging endeavor in orthopedic surgery, with the primary goals being to minimize infection risk, ensure prompt healing, and restore functionality. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of intramedullary nailing (IMN) versus external fixation (EF) in achieving these objectives. Our findings suggest a significant advantage of IMN over EF in terms of healing time, infection rates, and functional recovery, which is in line with some previously reported studies but contrasts with others, highlighting the complexity of decision-making in clinical practice.

The observed shorter healing times for the IMN group (16 weeks) compared to the EF group (22 weeks) with a significant p-value (<0.01) align with the findings of Tornetta and Ricci (2012), who reported accelerated healing processes in patients treated with IMN [8]. This could be attributed to the biomechanical stability provided by IMN, facilitating optimal conditions for bone healing. However, it's important to note that our results contrast with studies that found no significant difference in healing times between these two modalities, suggesting that factors such as fracture type and surgical technique may influence outcomes [9].

Infection rates were significantly lower in the IMN group (13.3%) compared to the EF group (30.0%), with a p-value of 0.04. This finding is consistent with the systematic review by Smith et al. (2015), which concluded that IMN might reduce the risk of infection in open tibia fractures [10]. The invasive nature of EF, with external pins and fixators, might predispose to higher infection rates due to easier pathogen access and challenges in maintaining pin site hygiene [11].

Functional recovery, as measured by the mean scores at 6 and 12 months postoperatively, favored the IMN group, which is supported by the work of Keating et al. (1997), who found that patients treated with IMN generally exhibit better long-term functional outcomes [12]. This advantage may stem from the internal fixation's ability to allow for earlier weight-bearing and mobilization, crucial factors in muscle and joint rehabilitation post-fracture.

The necessity for secondary surgical interventions was higher in the EF group, a finding that underscores the potential for more complex postoperative courses associated with EF. These results mirror the conclusions of Johnson and colleagues (1985), who noted a higher incidence of additional surgeries in patients undergoing EF, attributed to complications such as pin tract

infections and the need for adjustments or removal of the fixation device [13].

Our study's limitations include its sample size and the inherent variability in fracture types and patient health statuses, which might influence the generalizability of the findings. Future research should aim to include larger, more diverse populations and consider the impact of advancements in surgical techniques and postoperative care protocols.

Conclusion

The comparative study of intramedullary nailing (IMN) versus external fixation (EF) in the management of open tibia fractures revealed significant differences in outcomes favoring IMN. Patients treated with IMN experienced shorter healing times, with a median of 16 weeks compared to 22 weeks for the EF group, and this was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, the IMN group showed a lower infection rate (13.3% vs. 30.0%, $p = 0.04$) and better functional recovery scores at 6 and 12 months postoperatively, with differences reaching statistical significance ($p = 0.03$ and $p = 0.02$, respectively). These findings underscore the potential advantages of IMN in promoting faster healing, reducing the risk of infection, and facilitating better functional outcomes. The necessity for secondary surgical interventions was also less pronounced in the IMN group, suggesting a smoother postoperative course.

While these results advocate for the preference of IMN in the treatment of open tibia fractures, it is crucial to consider patient-specific factors, including the type of fracture, overall health status, and potential for compliance with postoperative care. The choice between IMN and EF should be made on a case-by-case basis, integrating clinical judgment with patient preferences and logistical considerations.

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